

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS OF GLOBAL ECONOMY DURING COVID-19

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Abstract

The COVID-19 in 2020 has caused a huge impact on the world economy. As the COVID-19 continues to rage around the world, major economies around the world experience a steep economic decline, rising unemployment, rising inflation, high prices of various commodities and the continued geopolitical penetration of countries during 2020-2021. This paper uses an empirical analysis using a 2-year panel data of global countries from 2020-2021 to conduct model regressions to derive the impact of the COVID-19 on key economic indicators such as the world economy, trade, inflation and unemployment, respectively, to fully substantiate the paper's argument. The study finds that the COVID-19 can dampen global economic growth, trade growth and increase the risk of rising unemployment and inflation in economies around the world. The study also found that opportunities for the digital economy in the light of COVID-19 and the economic policies introduced by countries.

Keywords: COVID-19; empirical analysis; economy; digital economy.

Introduction

The outbreak of COVID-19 at the end of 2019 is a serious challenge for the world. As of today, there are still some countries and regions in a worrying situation and no effective way has been found to control the world epidemic, the global economy is facing a major test and growth is stagnant. Starting in January 2020 to soothe the damage and impact of the COVID-19 on the economy, countries have adopted corresponding quantitative easing policies to stimulate the economy and keep it relatively stable. However, under the unconventional economic stimulus policies, it may be followed by huge fluctuations in the world capital markets, such as the beginning of July 2022, the United States began a comprehensive interest rate hike and tapering policy, resulting in the continuous return of the US dollar to the US market, in this situation the foreign exchange markets of all countries in the world have been hit to varying degrees, bringing more uncertainty to the world economic growth. Under the impact of the epidemic, the losses suffered by service-based economies have been enormous, with many emerging economies around the world facing the risk of national bankruptcy in the period 2020-2021.

Literature review

The impact of the COVID-19 on the world economy has been studied by many scholars, both domestic and foreign, in terms of the factors affecting economic development during this period. Since the outbreak of the COVID-19, most countries around the world have taken corresponding measures to restrict the movement of people in order to limit the exponential growth of pandemic cases, which has had different degrees of impact on the world economic operations and the world economic landscape. Qin Yu argues that the impact of

the epidemic on the economy is a short-term impact, for which effective epidemic control measures should be adopted and the right economic macroeconomic control measures should be taken to reduce the impact of the epidemic on economic growth [1]. Liu Di argues that the outbreak of the COVID-19 directly led to severe losses in the service industry, and that the reduction in demand for services indirectly reduced people's consumption demand, which in turn led to difficulties in returning to work for small and medium-sized enterprises and slowed down industrial development, resulting in job losses and a steep increase in structural and frictional unemployment [2]. Guo Zelin and others argue that the widespread spread of pandemics has multiple impacts on global economic activities, affecting the global division of labour and the existing global governance system, and challenging existing governance rules [3]. Regarding the economic impact of COVID-19 on countries or regions, Kistanov argues that Japan is one of the four developed countries in Asia with a high level of economic and social development and a high standard of living for its people. COVID-19 has had a new impact on the political situation in Japan, which has been forced to coordinate foreign economic and diplomatic strategies [4]. An Chunying argues that due to the COVID-19, the African region's economies may face an even greater test, with oil and commodity prices plummeting and tourism collapsing in African economies. To deal with the pandemic, Africa has used its national strength. Money from pay cuts for ministers was used to help the country fight off the economic and social damage caused by the COVID-19. One can imagine how serious the impact of the spread of the COVID-19 has been on African economies [5]. Ma, Wanqing argues that COVID-19 has important short-

term economic impacts on China's secondary industry, consumption and services, and international trade, and its long-term impacts depend on the global epidemic and its control [6]. Yu Ziqing believes that due to the outbreak of the pandemic, the world economy has been hit hard and the international trade situation has changed, with China as a major trading nation facing huge losses [7]. As Li Rong, Yu Ziqing and Gospodarik C.G point out that during the epidemic, the digital economy had a positive impact on the development of the global economy [8, 10]. This paper draws together relevant literature from various scholars and draws on various perspectives in the literature to examine the exogenous shocks of the COVID-19 and to empirically study the impact on global economic development.

Empirical analysis

Data sources and variable definitions. From the previous literature, there are many factors that influence the changes in the world economy, including

there are consumption, GDP level, trade prosperity, etc. And this pandemic is a major public health emergency that occurs globally with the fastest spread, the widest range of infection and the difficulty of prevention and control. It has the characteristics of rapid development and wide scope. This paper uses data from 106 countries worldwide for the period 2020-2021 for model regression analysis. The data for the COVID-19 is the excess number of deaths released by the World Health Organization (WHO) taken as a logarithmic value, the unemployment rate data is from the EPS database, and the other data is from the CSMAR database.

In this paper, we analyze GDP of 106 countries worldwide for the period 2020-2021 as the explained variable, excess mortality is selected as the explanatory variable, and CPI, M2 and exchange rate are selected as control variables. All variables are described in Table 1 and the calculations were made in Stata package.

Table 1

Variable definitions		
Type of variable	Name of variable	Variable codes
Explained variables	GDP of countries or regions	In_gdp
Explanatory variables	Excess mortality rates	In_covid
Control variables	CPI	In_cpi
	M2	In_M2
	Exchange rates	In_exrate
	Ex_in	In_exin

Research Model design. Having determined the definition and selection of variables through the previous study, the following empirical model is constructed in this paper.

$$GDP_{it} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 Covid_{it} + \beta_2 M2_{it} + \beta_3 Ex_in_{it} + \beta_4 cpi_{it} + \beta_5 Exrate_{it} \mu_i + \omega_i + \varepsilon_{it}$$

GDP_{it} —— the level of GDP in country i in year t

$Covid_{it}$ —— excess mortality rates

$M2_{it}$ —— Broad money

Ex_in_{it} —— export and import

cpi_{it} —— Consumer price index

μ_i —— Individual fixed effects items

ω_i —— Time fixed effects term

ε_{it} —— Residual term

3.3 Descriptive statistical analysis

Following the previous study, this paper analyses the data for each variable, including the explained variables GDP, total exports and imports, CPI, the explanatory variable excess mortality and including the control variables, for overall descriptive statistics as shown in Table 2.

Table 2

Descriptive statistics						
Variables	Variable definitions	Obs	Mean	Standard deviation	Minimum value	Maximum value
In_gdp	Economic growth	72	27.72301	1.550798	23.84561	31.32599
In_ex_in	Import and export	72	27.79192	1.878381	23.56941	31.53954
In_exrate	Exchange rates	72	3.793068	2.943233	.4402581	10.75221
In_Covid	Excess mortality	59	4.353483	1.147263	0	5.863631
In_M2	Broad money	72	12.09082	2.466971	8.204672	18.63096
In_CPI	Consumer Price Index	72	5.030975	.3508611	4.658711	5.979392

The results show that the maximum value of the variable economic growth (GDP) is 31.33; the minimum value is 23.85; and the standard deviation is 1.55, which indicates that there is a large gap in economic power between the various countries of the global economy, with the wealth of the lagging countries being much smaller than that of the developed countries. The

maximum value of imports and exports (ex_in) is 31.54; the minimum value is 23.57; and the standard deviation is 1.88, which indicates that there is a significant gap between countries' total imports and exports in the general context of the epidemic. For countries with more affluent domestic products, there are enough productive goods to meet domestic demand, while for

trade deficit countries, COVID-19 increases the trade deficit of small economies. The maximum and minimum values of exchange rates for the sample as a whole are 10.75 and 0.44 respectively, with a standard deviation of 2.94. This indicates that during the COVID-19, there were large differences in exchange rates for different countries, which may be due to different economic conditions in different countries. From the above descriptive statistics, it is not only clear that the world economy is performing poorly in the context of pandemic, but also that the world economic recovery is facing a very big challenge.

Baseline regressions analysis. This paper first uses benchmark regression analysis to examine whether the epidemic has had a negative impact on the global economy. Drawing on Liu Xueliang and Zhang Xiaojing [9] to model the impact of the 2003 SARS shock on economic growth, selecting GDP as the data indicator of economic impact. From the basic regressions, it can be seen that in equation (1) the regression analysis is the relationship between excess mortality and economic growth.

Table 2

Basic regression						
(1) ln_gdp	Coefficient	Std.err	t	P> t	[95% conf.interval]	
In_covid	-0.029	0.009	-3.35	0.001	-0.045	-0.012
In_CPI	0.690	0.169	4.09	0.000	-0.359	1.021
In_exin	-0.047	0.006	-7.27	0.000	-0.060	-0.035
In_exrate	-0.871	0.506	-17.20	0.000	-0.970	-0.772
In_m2	0.841	0.057	14.84	0.000	0.730	0.772
_cons	19.126	1.015	18.84	0.000	17.14	28.776
Sigma_u	0.425					
Sigma_e	0.036					
rho	0.995					

The results can be output directly from table 2, as shown in table 3.

Table 3

Results of Basic regression		(1)
		ln_gdp
In_covid		-0.029*** (-3.35)
ln_cpi		0.690*** (4.09)
In_exin		-0.047*** (-7.27)
In_exrate		-0.871*** (-17.20)
In_m2		0.841*** (14.84)
_cons		19.13*** (18.84)
N		106

Note: Standard errors in parentheses, * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

The results show that in (1) it can be found that the regression coefficient is -0.029 and excess mortality inhibits global economic growth at the 1% level of significance. This would suggest that global economic growth has been affected by COVID-19 and is negatively related.

Predictive Analysis. Based on the previous regression analysis coefficients and model, the regression equation can be established as:

$$GDP_{it} = -0.029 * Covid_{it} + 0.841 * M2_{it} - 0.047 * Ex_in_{it} + 0.69 * cpi_{it} - 0.871 * Exrate_{it} + 19.13$$

The regression equation allows for the within-group prediction data to be made and Table 4 shows the predicted results.

Table 4

Predicted results of the modelling				
Variable	Mean	Std. dev	Min	Max
Loggdp pre	27.52653	1.212689	24.9809	30.03777
Loggdp	27.72301	1.550798	23.84561	31.32599

From the table, we can see that the difference between the predicted and true values is small for the mean, median, maximum and minimum values, so we can assume that the prediction model works well.

The above content presents an empirical and regression analysis of the study to verify that COVID-19 will have a negative impact on the global economy. And the feasibility of the model is demonstrated by using the model to make within-group predictions. Recommendations will then be made based on the findings of the study in conjunction with existing national economic policies.

Opportunities for the digital economy for China. With the arrival of the epidemic causing huge restrictions on travel, digital technology is being used extensively in epidemic prevention and control, work and life. During the epidemic, the digital economy has developed rapidly, radiated widely and had a deep impact, and is becoming a key force in restructuring global factor resources, reshaping the global economic structure and changing the global competitive landscape. At the micro level, new technologies such as the Internet, big data and cloud computing continue to promote economies of scale and scope in various industries, which can also make use of the long-tail effect to

promote the growth of industrial profits, while improving the price mechanism and optimising the matching relationship between supply and demand, thereby improving the equilibrium of the economy. Take China as an example, in 2020, in the midst of the adjustment period of the world economic crisis and the impact of the COVID-19 epidemic, the development of China's digital economy bucked the trend and achieved remarkable results, reaching 39.2 trillion yuan, an increase of 3.3 trillion yuan compared to 2019, and accounting for 38.6% of GDP, an increase of 2.4 percentage points year-on-year. In 2008, the number of Internet users in China jumped to the number one position in the world, reaching 253 million. The early development of the digital economy took shape with the Internet and information technology, and the design of policies to support the development of the digital economy in China began with information technology. During the epidemic, many local regulatory documents for the digital economy have been issued by local governments in various provinces in China, covering specific measures to support the development of the digital economy, methods of managing special funds, and investments in new infrastructure (Table 4).

Table 4

Methods and Policy for digital economy

Time	Policy	Contents
April 2020	Opinions on building a more complete institutional mechanism for the market-based allocation of factors	1. Vigorously cultivate the new digital economy 2. Deeply promote the digital transformation of enterprises 3. Create a data supply chain, lead the flow of materials, talents, technology and capital with the flow of data, and form a digital ecosystem with upstream and downstream industrial chain and cross-industry integration
July 2020	Opinions on supporting the healthy development of new industries and models, activating the consumer market to drive employment expansion	We are fostering an industrial platform development ecology, accelerating the pace of digital transformation of traditional enterprises, creating "virtual" industrial parks and industrial clusters that cross physical boundaries, and developing an "unmanned economy" based on new technologies.
August 2021	Implementation Plan of Beijing on Accelerating the Construction of a Global Digital Economy Benchmark City	The world's first "blueprint" for the development of a digital economy benchmark city. The plan specifies Beijing's strategic plan for accelerating the development of the digital economy, creating "six highlands" that will lead the development of the global digital economy, and building a global digital economy benchmark city by 2030
January 2022	"The 14th Five-Year Plan" for the Development of the Digital Economy	It is proposed that by 2025, the value added of core industries in the digital economy will reach 10% of GDP, a market system for data elements will be initially established, the digital transformation of industries will reach a new level, the level of digital industrialization will be significantly improved, digital public services will be more inclusive and equal, and the governance system of the digital economy will be more perfect.

Source: author's development based on policy documents

The sudden outbreak of COVID-19 is a rare major international public health event in recent years, and countries have introduced policies from different perspectives.

1) Epidemic Prevention and Control Policy

As of 5 November 2022, China is adhering to the general strategy of "preventing external imports and internal rebound". This means reducing imports from abroad and preventing a rebound of the epidemic at

home. In order to facilitate the travel of people, in 2020 China will launch the "Health Code", which is based on actual real data and is generated by citizens through their own online declaration, which will be audited by the back-office and generated as their own QR code. The QR code is used as an electronic proof of personal travel and can be declared once and used throughout the city. Even with a health code, each city has different entry policies. For example, in Beijing, Entry to Beijing

is strictly limited by the history of residence in the area where the new indigenous New Coronavirus infected person was living within 7 days prior to entry, a negative nucleic acid test within 48 hours to prove a green code for Beijing Healthbot, home quarantine for 3 days after entering Beijing, and two tests for 3 days after entering Beijing are launched (one nucleic acid test within 24 hours of entering Beijing, one nucleic acid test within a 24-hour interval After 24 hours, one nucleic acid test within 72 hours). Upon entry into Beijing and the emergence of risks related to the epidemic, suspected symptoms are reported at the first opportunity. This is only the prevention and control policy for entry into one city, so you can imagine how strict China's prevention and control of COVID-19 outbreak is. On 23 March 2020, the UK officially declared a three-week state of lockdown, during which all major gatherings were cancelled, citizens were advised to implement a policy of social distancing and isolation, and people who could afford to work from home adopted a home isolation policy. However, on 19 July 2021, the UK government lifts most of the prevention and control measures, no longer mandating the wearing of masks and allowing more businesses to reopen.

2) Macroeconomic policy in different developed countries during the pandemic COVID-19

The United States. In terms of GDP, the US Treasury, Fiscal Services and Internal Revenue Service (IRS) quickly issued three rounds of benefits to direct payments to households and individuals due to the impact of COVID-19. One is that under the March 2020 CARES Act, the U.S. government provides economic impact payments of \$1,200 per eligible adult and \$500 per child under the age of 17. In addition, in December 2020, Congress passed the COVID-19 Tax Credit Act of 2020 (CRTR), which provides an additional \$600 for each eligible adult and \$600 for each child under the age of 17. Third, with Biden in office, the American Relief Plan Act of 2021 (ARP) provides a \$1,400 economic impact payment for eligible individuals, \$2,800 for married couples filing jointly, and \$1,400 for dependents, including adult dependents. In the fiscal years 2020 and 2021, the US Treasury disbursed a total of \$274.654 billion and \$569.508 billion in EIP, respectively.

In terms of unemployment, *the United States* has also carried out large-scale unemployment compensation. All the workers who lost their jobs due to the epidemic can receive an additional unemployment compensation of \$600 per person per week on top of the state unemployment compensation. Beginning in March 2021, the ARP extends unemployment compensation and gives individuals with adjusted gross income of less than \$150,000 an exemption from federal income tax on unemployment benefits received in 2020 of less than \$10,200. *Germany* gave up the principle of fiscal balance that it had insisted on for many years. In order to cope with the impact of the epidemic, the German government gave up the two fiscal balance principles of "Black zero" and "debt brake" that it had adhered to for more than a decade, and launched the largest economic aid package since the Second World War,

totaling 750 billion euros, among which 156 billion euros was raised through debt, mainly for government supplementary budget, and 600 billion euros was used for corporate aid. This includes €400 bn in corporate guarantees, €100bn in corporate equity bail-outs and €100 bn in state-backed loans through Germany's state-owned KfW bank.

In response to unemployment, the German government has also provided various tax relief measures for businesses, independent workers and freelancers to improve their mobility. On the employee side, the Government has introduced temporary regulations to simplify and increase the number of short-time allowance recipients, which reached a record high of about 6 million in April 2020. The German government is also providing €255 million in "short-term work" subsidies and €50 billion in small business subsidies to small business owners and self-employed people who have been hit hard by the pandemic. On monetary policy, in addition to measures at the eurozone level, Germany has cut interest rates from 0.25 percent to zero; Within the World Financial Fund, €100 bn has been set aside to take direct stakes in the worst-affected companies and strengthen their capital positions.

Facing the severe domestic epidemic and economic risks, *the French government* vowed to protect and save its economy "whatever the cost". In terms of fiscal policy, a €45 billion fiscal plan and a €300 billion national guarantee plan have been proposed to support COVID-19 patients, affected micro-enterprises, freelance and independent workers, including direct subsidies, deferment of social security and taxes, payment of rent and utilities, and extension of unemployment benefits. On monetary policy, 120 billion euros of asset purchases by the end of 2020 will be supported by the European Central Bank. A further €750bn programme of asset purchases of private and public sector securities. It relaxed asset and collateral standards for the banking sector and expanded the scope of asset purchases and refinancing. Support banks in renegotiating bank loans to small businesses.

Great Britain launched the "biggest government intervention in the market" since the Second World War to protect businesses and help people tide over the difficulties, and an unprecedented fiscal policy package. These include: £5bn of extra funding for the NHS and other public services, £27bn of direct grants for hard-hit small businesses and sick leave compensation for staff, almost £7bn of support for the vulnerable and 80% of the earnings of self-employed and business employees over three months (up to £2,500 a month). On monetary policy, the Bank rate has been cut by 65 basis points to 0.1%, the lowest level in more than 300 years. The central bank's holdings of British government bonds and non-financial corporate bonds increased by £ 200 billion. Provide £330 billion of loans and guarantees to businesses, which alone amounts to 1.5% of the UK's annual gross national product, while launching the Coronavirus Business Interruption Loan Scheme with high street banks to support the financing needs of small and medium-sized enterprises.

Japan enacted the biggest economic stimulus bill since World War II. Since the outbreak of the pandemic, Japan has passed two emergency response plans on 13 February and 10 March 2020, respectively, with a total value of about 446 billion yen, focusing on supporting strengthening the response capacity of the medical system, increasing paid leave and compensating working parents affected by school closures, and providing subsidies for companies to maintain employment. On 7 April 2020, the Japanese government approved a 108 trillion yen emergency economic plan, described as the country's biggest ever stimulus package. The plan is divided into two parts: an "emergency support phase" during the outbreak and a "V-shaped recovery phase" after the outbreak has subsided. The first part mainly supports families and small and medium-sized enterprises affected by the epidemic. The standard of supplementary income is 300,000 yen per household. Small and medium-sized enterprises with a big drop in turnover can get a subsidy of up to 2 million yen, and freelancers and self-employed people with a big drop in income can get a subsidy of up to 1 million yen. In addition, the government will increase the level of employment subsidies for companies, allow companies to defer the payment of income tax and social insurance premiums, expand financial support for small and medium-sized companies, and provide assistance to airlines whose performance has deteriorated. In monetary policy, the Bank of Japan announced that it will keep short-term interest rates at minus 0.1 percent and keep long-term interest rates at around zero by buying long-term government bonds.

Conclusions and recommendations

This paper examines the impact of the COVID-19 on world economic growth, international trade and employment using data from 106 national economies over the period 2020-2021. The study finds that, in general, the COVID-19 can slow world economic growth and impede international trade at this stage, while increasing unemployment. In a partial view, the available data is divided into developed and non-developed countries, and it is found that the impact of the COVID-19 on non-developed countries is more costly. Therefore this paper puts forward relevant recommendations respectively. Firstly, in the case of global value chain reversal, the focus should be on promoting the development of new types of industries in each country, accelerating the reconfiguration of global industrial chains and global supply chains, and advocating diversified investment to achieve the purpose of risk stabilization. Secondly, we should accelerate the resumption

of global industries, enhance the flow of capital and technicians between countries, accelerate economic globalization to integrate both developing and developed countries into this world economy, and accelerate the development of world economic integration and national cooperation. Third, to avoid international conflicts, countries to prevent geopolitical conflicts and prevent the emergence of unilateralist ideas.

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